

A Science Gateway Aiding The Examination of Substance Use, Mental Health, and Crisis Care For The State of Hawaii

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Abstract—The State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard is an interactive online platform that provides data on substance use, mental health, and crisis care in Hawaii. The dashboard was co-developed by the Hawaii Department of Health, the University of Hawaii Thompson School of Social Work and Public Health, University of Hawaii Center On Aging, and the Hawaii Data Science Institute as part of the Overdose Data to Action project funded by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. The dashboard integrates data from multiple sources, including local providers, national datasets, and state agencies and allows users to explore trends, patterns, and disparities in behavioral health indicators across the state. The dashboard also incorporates automated updates and data quality checks to ensure timely and accurate information. The dashboard aims to inform prevention strategies, policy decisions, and community awareness on behavioral health issues in Hawaii.

Index Terms—data science

I. INTRODUCTION

Behavioral health is a broad term that encompasses the emotional, psychological, and social aspects of health or well-being, including mental health and substance use. Behavioral health problems such as substance use disorders, mental illnesses, and co-occurring disorders affect millions of people in the United States and have significant impacts on indi-

viduals, families, communities, and society. According to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA), in 2020, an estimated 40.3 million people aged 12 or older had a substance use disorder (SUD) in the past year, 52.9 million people aged 18 or older had any mental illness (AMI) in the past year, and 17 million people aged 18 or older had both a SUD and an AMI (co-occurring disorders) in the past year [1]. Moreover, drug overdose deaths have increased dramatically in recent years, reaching $\geq 100,000$ deaths from January 2015 to January 2022 [2].

In Hawaii, substance use and behavioral health problems are also prevalent and pose significant challenges for public health. According to SAMHSA's National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH), in 2018-2019, Hawaii ranked in the top 10 state for methamphetamine use in the past among people aged 12 or older (0.77%), top 30 in past month illicit drug use among people aged 12 or older (10.6%), past year serious mental illness among adults aged 18 or older (3.45%), and past year suicidal ideation among adults aged 18 or older (3.85%) [3]. Furthermore, Hawaii has seen an increasing trend in unintentional drug overdose deaths from 2018 to 2021, with 238 deaths reported in 2021 compared to 196 in 2018 [4].

To help address these substance use and behavioral health

Fig. 1: The State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard overview page. The overview displays current trends for top substance use and mental health indicators related to overdose and emergency department discharges.

problems, it is essential to have timely and comprehensive data that can inform prevention strategies, policy decisions, and community awareness. However, behavioral health data are often fragmented across multiple sources and systems, making it difficult to access, integrate, analyze, and disseminate effectively. Moreover, behavioral health data are often subject to delays, gaps, inconsistencies, and inaccuracies that limit their utility and validity.

To overcome these challenges and enhance substance use and behavioral health surveillance in Hawaii, the State of Hawaii Department of Health (DOH), the University of Hawaii Thompson School of Social Work and Public Health, Center On Aging (COA), and the Hawaii Data Science Institute (HDSI) have developed the State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard [5], an interactive online platform that provides data on substance use, mental health, and crisis care in Hawaii. The dashboard was co-developed by these partners as part of the Overdose Data to Action (OD2A) project funded by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). The OD2A project aims to expand public health surveillance and use

data to drive prevention strategies for drug-related misuse and overdose morbidity and mortality [6]. The dashboard integrates data from multiple sources, including local providers, national datasets, and state agencies and allows users to explore trends, patterns, and disparities in behavioral health indicators across the state. The dashboard also incorporates automated updates and data quality checks to ensure timely and accurate information. The dashboard aims to inform prevention strategies, policy decisions, and community awareness on behavioral health issues in Hawaii. This paper presents the State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard and an overview of its design and features.

II. DASHBOARD DESIGN AND INTERFACE

A. Data Storage

The data warehouse infrastructure that stores and collects substance use and related mental health information consists of a Microsoft Azure government cloud Microsoft SQL instance. It is combined with Microsoft Data Factory for automating the ingestion of data from public and private data providers

Fig. 2: Substance Use interactive data dashboard visuals for A) Unintentional/Undetermined Overdose Deaths for the State of Hawaii from 2018-2021 from the Wide-ranging ONline Data for Epidemiologic Research (WONDER) dataset overview by year and county. B.) Unintentional/Undetermined Overdose Deaths for the State of Hawaii from 2018-2021 from WONDER dataset breakdown by year, substance, demographics (age, gender and race) and county.

[7] at appropriate periods of update (daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, and yearly). The Microsoft Data Factory executes R and Python codes developed by DOH and HI-DSI for fetching or processing surveillance data related to substance use and overdose data.

B. Web Interface

The data warehouse serves the data to Microsoft Power BI reports, hosted in the Hawaii DOH Microsoft Azure Power BI server. These reports are embedded as iframes within web-pages managed by a WordPress content management system hosted on the Hawaii DOH infrastructure. This WordPress instance serves the content to stakeholders via web browsers as a website (<https://bh808.hawaii.gov/>). The website is organized into about, help, static reports and 5 dynamic data sections: Overview, Substance Use (SU), Mental Health (MH), Co-Occurring SU/MH, and Crisis. The Overview page is the landing page and summarizes the purpose of the State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard and top-level trends related to substance overdose and use, mental health, and co-occurrence of substance use and mental health diagnosis (fig. 1). The substance use page includes interactive information on emergency department discharges related to substance use, substance overdoses and data related to client usage of the DOH alcohol and drug abuse division services. The mental health page include information on emergency department discharges related to mental health disorders and consumer usage of the DOH adult mental health divisions services. The co-occurring SU and MH page presents emergency depart discharge where substance use and mental health are both present along with DOH services usage for adult mental health division and the alcohol and drug abuse division. The crisis page highlights data on crisis call center line

statistics and crisis mobile outreach dispatches. The Power BI reports enable interactive presentation of the different data sets through charts, graphs, and tables with dynamic filters so that stakeholders can explore the information in more depth (fig. 2).

C. Navigation and Filtering

The controls of each dashboard are essentially the same. Each dashboard data view has tabs along the top allowing users to select which aspect fits what they are investigating. Users can filter the datasets using drop-down multi-select filters or for support views a user can click on a bar of a chart, a row of a table, or an item as appropriate. Upon filter selection the other values adjust according to the applied filters. To accomplish additional filtering users can combine filter drop-down options or for supporting visuals hold down the control key (CTRL) and click on any additional graph bars, table rows or items they desire to to drill-down further. The use of these interactive filters allows users to answer questions related to substance use and overdoses based on substance types, mental health diagnoses, and demographics categories for specific years and specific islands in the state (fig. 2 and fig. 3).

III. IMPACT

Within 9 months its beta release in October of 2022, the State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard has had more than 10,000 visitors and 15,000 page visits. Furthermore, the dashboard has garnered interest from state officials and the news media related to substance use, overdoses related to methamphetamine and mixed drug toxicity. This large interest from visitors to the site and external stakeholders requesting communications related to the dashboard highlight the effectiveness of this method for presenting surveillance data to the OD2A and wider stakeholder community in Hawaii.

Fig. 3: Substance Use interactive data dashboard visuals for A) Emergency Department Discharges for the State of Hawaii from 2018-2021 related to substance use overview by substance, age, sex, year and county. B.) Emergency Department Discharges for the State of Hawaii from 2018-2021 related to the co-occurrence of substance use and mental health diagnosis - current selection of mental health diagnosis is “Mood (Affective) Disorder” with corresponding, substances, age, sex, county and year information.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented the State of Hawaii Behavioral Health Dashboard, a collaborative project that provides data on substance use, mental health, and crisis care in Hawaii. We have described the features and functions of the dashboard. The dashboard is a valuable tool that can help address the challenges and opportunities in improving the behavioral health outcomes of Hawaii’s population. Furthermore, the dashboard is not a static product, but a dynamic platform that can be updated and enhanced with new data, indicators, and functionalities, therefore, we will continue to collaborate and seek feedback from users and experts to ensure that the dashboard meets their needs and expectations.

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